

The Impact of Advertising on Consumer Buying Behaviour

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Fariha Arshad**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: farihaarshad2233@gmail.com

⁽²⁾ **Dr. Masood Hassan**

PhD, IoBM, Karachi, Pakistan and Visiting Faculty Greenwich, Karachi, Pakistan, Email:

masoodhassan1@hotmail.com (**Corresponding Author**)

⁽³⁾ **Muhammad Zaid**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: zedd.saleem993@gmail.com

⁽⁴⁾ **Kulsoom Nadeem**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: kulsumnadeem21@gmail.com

⁽⁵⁾ **Osama Anees Darbari**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: osamadarbari9@gmail.com

Abstract:

This report below discusses the impact of advertising on consumer buying behavior. One of the major strategies of various brands for the product's promotion is advertisements. The role of mass advertisement is to grab the attention of the consumer for the product, make a sure prolonged connection with the customers, and also for recalling the particular product in the mind of the customer. It proceeds to determine the impact of advertising in convincing the attitude of the consumer for the purpose of purchasing the desired product. This report below recommends that the target audience should be extensively reached for the purpose of knowing their pattern of consumption as well as behavior towards services and products for the purpose of taking place effective advertising. Also, the effort must be more directed over emotional advertisements, since customers' patronage is mainly induced through their feelings and emotions. With the vast increase in advancement of technology, effective advertising has now extremely significant to be able to have benefits of competition, hence the requirement for research of this report.

Keywords: Advertising, Consumer Buying Behavior, Target Audience, Emotional Response, Environmental Response.

Introduction

Advertisements are referred to as one of the most topical brand strategies for the purpose of promoting a particular product or service (Lee, Fernandez, & Martin, 2002). To ensure lengthened association with the customer, to recall the product in the mind of the consumer, or to get the attention of the product is the purpose of advertising (Barroso & Llobet, 2012). The way organizations and businesses communicate with their customers with the help of advertising has somehow changed throughout the years through television, printing press, radio, and social media (Lee et al., 2002). Advertising is much more adaptable today as compared to old times. People are exposed to marketing wherever or whenever, even if they need it or not, also many times without even observing (Seegercrantz, 2013). The effect of the digital outbreak on the sector of advertising has vastly changed the accessibility as well as the reach of broader consumers that are inspired by the content of social media (Barroso et al., 2012). Nowadays, many organizations, government sectors, and enterprises have created good efforts for advertisement. The advertisement has variations of purposes, looking for the formation of constant demand, impact on attitudes for the purpose of meeting the aim of advertising, and affirmative changes effect on advertising (Lee et al., 2002). The purpose of advertising is to sales of a particular product or service through advertisers and also to provide information along with the repayment via non-human media (Barroso et al., 2012).

The classification of advertising is divided into different ways of viewpoints; one, advertising is considered as a presentation of non-human as well as promotion along with the collection of ideas, services, or any product through the advertisement. Two, the advertisement is referred to as the persuasion or information handled by

mass media from viewpoint of the communication (Wright, 2016). Yet, advertising is considered to work from the viewpoint of communication as well as marketing also to provide getting information to the group through different sorts of media by individuals that are considered as impersonal conversation, non-profit doing organizations, and enterprises (Barroso, 2008). Also, advertising is defined as a vast spreading of factuality to add not just non-profit making advertisements but profit-making advertisements as well followed by expanded marketing application scope as well as the development of the theory of communication (Lee et al., 2002). Advertising is considered the main element of communication object between the consumer and the producer (Kotler, Keller, Koshy, & Jha, 2009). Advertising is referred to as a promotion strategy that works as the main tool in making awareness of the product in the mind of the customer for the purpose of making decisions to purchase (Barroso, 2008).

Advertising, public relations, and sales promotion are tools for mass communication utilized by marketers. Through mass media, advertising influences viewers, but TV is the strongest medium for advertisement and has mass reach (Odunsi, 2020). Advertising can affect the behavior of an individual, the culture of the country, and also lifestyle (Latif & Abideen, 2011). An organization can increase the brand of their service or product by investing in promotional work for the purpose of competing in a customer market that is ruled by advertising (Hussainy, Riaz, Kazi & Herani, 2008). The most important target of advertisers is to reach customers as well as influence the awareness of the customer, buying behavior, and attitude. The main preoccupation of advertisers is to keep customers' interest in their services or products by spending on advertisements (Barroso et al., 2012). Advertisers are also required to know what influence the behavior of the consumer. It has the strength to contribute to the brand choice of the customer. Advertisement effect on consumer behavior (Latif et al., 2011). Advertising affects consumer buying behavior. It affects the change of brand frequently in the memory of the people. Brand memories contain those associations which are interconnected to the brand name in the mind of the consumer. These cognitions of brands influence the steps which are considering, evaluating, and final purchasing the product (Romaniuk & Sharp, 2003).

The main purpose of advertisers is to reach their customers and influence their attitude, awareness, and buying behavior. The preoccupation of the advertisers is to keep the interest of an individual in their products by spending over advertising. Advertisers need to know what attracts customers' behavior. Advertising has the power to contribute to the customer brand choice (Latif et al., 2011). Some companies don't attach significance to the purpose of advertising their service or product and this has a counter impact on their output regarding sales of the particular product (Barroso et al., 2012). Others utilize various advertising media such as TV, newspapers, the internet, billboards, magazines, etc. for the purpose of conveying the message of the product to their customers or target audience (Odunsi, 2020). Organizations spend the main set of their budget on the strategies of advertising for the purpose of promoting their product. These strategies influence customer buying behavior (Chukwu, Kanu, & Ezeabogu, 2019). Customer buying behavior is considered as the physical, mental and emotional activities that a person connects while selecting, buying, and disposing of a product aiming to satisfy the desire and requirement of the consumer (Rai, 2013). For effective advertising, consumer behavior can be analyzed for the purpose of knowing why customers act in a specific manner under specific circumstances (Chukwu et al., 2019).

Advertisers make an advertisement that contains an emotional connection with the consumer. Positive advertisement emotional appeals and gives a good brand cue as well as stimulates type-based processing (Latif et al., 2011). Consumer buying behavior is impacted by some economic factors such as the price of the product, income-expenditure pattern, complimentary product price, the elasticity of demand, and substitute goods (Barroso et al., 2012). Consumer buying behavior is also impacted by psychological factors, attitudes as well as learning for instance placement and positioning of the product (Rai, 2013). It is significant for advertising managers to get the attention of the customer through sales promotion as well as advertisement in a competitive market. Advertising is to do things from the viewpoint of communication as well as marketing also to provide getting information to the group through different sorts of media by individuals that are considered as impersonal conversation, non-profit doing organizations, and enterprises (Barroso, 2008). A quality amount spent on advertising. Digital media platforms' trend is growing for advertisement (Odunsi, 2020). Mass media

and advertising influence their audience through their advertisement, but TV is the most essential medium for advertisement and has mass reach (Latif & Abideen, 2011). The most essential aim of advertisers is to reach customers as well as influence the awareness of the customer, buying behavior, and attitude. The main preoccupation of advertisers is to keep customers' interest in their services or products by spending on advertisements (Barroso et al., 2012). Advertisers are also required to know what influence the behavior of the consumer. It has the strength to contribute to the brand choice of the customer (Latif et al., 2011). Advertising can affect the behavior of an individual, the culture of the country, and also lifestyle (Odunsi, 2020). An organization can increase the brand of their service or product by investing in promotional work for the purpose of competing in a customer market that is ruled by advertising (Hussainy, Riaz, Kazi, & Herani, 2008). Marketers intend to achieve a high top of recalling the product name in the audience's mind through advertisement (Rai, 2013). Therefore, advertisements are considered a critical part of strategic marketing, specifically in business to customer context (Kotler et al., 2009).

Advertising

Advertising is considered a promotional strategy which uses in making awareness of the product in the consumer's mind for the purpose of making buying decisions (Latif et al., 2011). Advertising is a tool for communication used by advertisers/marketers. Advertising affects the attitude and behavior of an individual as well as lifestyle. Advertising is the main form of communication between a user of a particular product and the producer (Ayanwale, Alimi, & Ayanbimipe, 2005). The product should be a well-known brand for a company; the advertisers must put their investment in their promotional work, especially in advertisements (Hussein et al., 2008). Advertising has the strength to put in the choice of the brand among customers (Latif et al., 2011). Studies defined advertising that it's communication, social, economic, public relations, marketing or persuasion, and an information process (Ayanwale et al., 2005).

Dunn and Barban (1987) further defined advertising as it's a paid as well as non-personal communication by different media through business companies, non-profit corporation, and individuals as well, who are in a kind of recognized in the message of advertising and who expect to give information it persuades person of a particular audience. Studies discussed that a message of advertising is to create a fundamental awareness regarding the product or service inside of the mind of the particular customer as well as to acknowledge it to them (Ayanwale et al., 2005). The advertisement provides a key tool in making awareness of the product or service as well as situations in the mind of the consumer to make a final decision on what to buy or what not (Dunn et al., 1987). Advertising is a paid and non-personal kind where concepts, information, products or services, and ideas are conveyed by media through a recognized behavior (Ayanwale et al., 2005). Advertising through TV allows messages of advertisement for the purpose of reaching a vast amount of audience or customers and advertising is a good way to promote goods, products, organizations, ideas, services, etc (Dunn et al., 1987).

Consumer Buying Behaviour

Consumer buying behavior is considered as the physical, emotional, and mental activities that a person engages in while choosing, buying and product and service disposing of for the purpose of satisfying their desires and requirements (Arnould & Thompson, 2005). Consumer behavior includes buying and different other activities of people that engage in the process of exchanging related consumption. Studies discussed consumer behavior as the process that involved when a person or group chooses, buys, utilizes, or disposes of a product, idea, or service for the purpose of satisfying the needs and desires of the consumer (Pickett-Baker & Ozaki, 2008). Consumer buying behavior is impacted by some economic elements, for instance, the price of the product, income-expenditure pattern, price of complementary products, the elasticity of demand, and substitute goods (Arnould et al., 2005). Consumer behavior is also impacted by some psychological factors, perceptions learning, and attitudes (Pickett et al., 2008). Consumer buying behavior is impacted by social as well as cultural factors that impact a person in purchasing decisions but decide the type of product to purchase (Arnould et al., 2005).

Emotional Response

The emotional response in advertising is considered one of the effective kinds of integrated marketing communication that encourage customers emotionally to purchase a product or service (Moore, 2004). The extract of advertising is to produce brand awareness, selection, and preference for a particular product. Attitude towards the advertisement is very influential in the research of marketing and advertising (Rahmi, Tayeb, & Amerkhail, 2020). Since the aim of the advertisement is to create an attitude that is positive towards the brand and advertisement after that a positive emotional response towards the advertisement might be a good measure of effective advertising (Moore, 2004). This might be the reason why the fundamental purpose of advertising is to motivate customers to purchase products and services and produce awareness (Goldsmith et al., 2002). The ability of the customer to recall the particular advertisement of the brand is another element of effective advertisement that produces an emotional response (Moore, 2004).

The level to which customers make the decisions regarding products depends upon the importance of recalling the brand which may lead to the particular brand awareness (Rahmi et al., 2020). The awareness about brand helps to make sure to recall that which has the competitive benefit upon those brands that a person cannot easily recall. Positive behavior towards advertisement usually has more ability to recall an advertisement rather than a negative attitude towards the particular brand (Goldsmith et al., 2002). Indication has been discovered suitable under different producing situations for the purpose of brand recalling advertisement as well as good chance of brand to get back of any customer when various other attributes are connected to the particular brand, which produces brand association (Rahmi et al., 2020). One of the most effective elements in the advertisement is emotional advertising; the reason is it enables customers to give emotional responses toward a particular product (Goldsmith et al., 2002).

Environmental Response

The environmental response gives particular kinds of experiences to customers which are used for the purpose of promoting as well as selling products and services (Adelaar, Chang, Lancendorfer, Lee, & Morimoto, 2003). Businesses offer customers particular kinds of media experiences that are used for the purpose of setting up the level that encourages the selling of a particular product or service (Danaher, Danaher, Smith, & Loaiza-Maya, 2020). A special kind of marketing research has been made to explain the impacts of various environmental conditions such as in atmosphere in retailing shops as well as background music while a customer is purchasing (Adelaar et al., 2003). Sense processes for instance touch, sight, and sound can impact user experience, the production rate can impact user experience, and the production rate can impact the user for getting information regarding advertisement (Danaher et al., 2020).

The psychological environmental model represents these. This representation is applicable to this lyric's music, video as well as music, which are strongly interconnected to each other and are presented in advertisements (Adelaar et al., 2003). Studies found that the environmental psychology model gives a good concept regarding emotional response than the research of traditional marketing (Danaher et al., 2020). The environmental psychology model suggests that the environmental factors, for instance, retailing stores make an emotional level in the mind of an individual that can divide into arousal, buying situation, pleasure, or dominance (Adelaar et al., 2003). This environment psychology model defines the media which gives awareness that is described by the mixture of touch, sound, and sight sources (Danaher et al., 2020). It covers different stages of visual as well as verbal media messages, by which people receive information. The visual and verbal messages impact customers' mindset about the environment stimuli (Adelaar et al., 2003).

Brand awareness

Often looked on to a discussion of strategic advertising, brand awareness is a critical consideration. Brand awareness is perhaps thought of as the likeability of a customer for the purpose of identifying a brand under a group in plenty of detail to create a purchase (Aaker, 1996). It is significant to remember that enough detail does not always need recognition of the brand name. Frequently it is not more of a visual picture of the package

that encourages a response to a brand (Keller, 1993). Furthermore, recalling the brand name is not significantly needed the reason is brand awareness may begin through brand identification. When a brand is identified while buying, brand awareness might not be needed to recall a brand (Aaker, 1996). This is a significant point in considering brand awareness as a communication purpose. Brand awareness is considered as the first as well as the prerequisite aspect of the whole knowledge about the brand in the mind of the consumer, reflecting their capability to identify the brand in various situations: the probability that a name of the brand will pop up to the mind and the relief with which it does so (Keller, 1993). Brand awareness is considered according to the various ways in which customers remember a brand, which may involve recognition of the brand, dominant brand, and top-of-the-mind brand (Aaker, 1996).

Product placement

Placement is considered as the purposeful combination of business content under non-business settings, that is a service or product plug created through the fusion of entertainment as well as advertising (Ginosar & Levi-Faur, 2010). Product placement is also considered in program sponsoring, product brand placement, brand entertainment, and product integration are also considered marketing activities in promotion and advertising where a brand name, package, product, signage, or various trademark merchandise is connected into as well as utilized contextually under in the motion picture, TV, or various other media vehicles for advertising activities (Stephen & Coote, 2005). The involved viewers get disclosed to the product and brand while the natural movie, television program, or content vehicle process in product placement (Ginosar et al., 2010). Product placement in famous mass media gives exposure to a strong target audience and brand of the shows being consumed and utilized in their natural settings (Stephen et al., 2005). Lastly, the product or brand, or service is seen as a quality of recognition with characters approving and using the product placement (Ginosar et al., 2010).

Sensory Stimulation Advertisement

The senses play a very major role in customers' perceptions as well as exert a potential influence over purchasing decisions (Wei, Liu, Xu, Li, & Cao, 2022). Nowadays, sensory marketing is considered an important tool for encouraging the connection between customers and the brand by stimulating other senses and producing emotions. Sensory marketing includes applying a marketing campaign that appeals to the customer's five senses which are touch, sight, taste, sound, and smell (Wei et al., 2022). Sensory marketing includes various techniques that are utilized to reach the consumer's senses as well as influence their attitude based on how the tactics and brand create them feel. Using media senses in marketing and advertising campaigns can highly influence the viewers and the decision of the viewers as well to purchase a product. A specific sensory appeal can attract how people recognize the activity or object when linked with the particular sensory experience (Krishna, Cian, & Sokolova, 2016).

The sensory appeal is impactful in product promotion to the customer, which is why advertisement of sensory appeal can get great outcomes. Senses advertisement and marketing is an effective yet simple approach for the purpose of influencing customers to buy a particular product or service. It is the most potent sense in the advertisement world (Wei et al., 2022). Fortunately, it is considered one of the simplest marketing and advertising senses to create the most of. To find out, make sure the corporate website is appealing and beautiful to the consumer, or recruit an experienced to design the social apps as well as graphics for advertisement (Krishna et al., 2016). Sensory advertisement is the greatest way for the brand to activate the consumer's emotion and set up engagement (Wei et al., 2022).

Relationship between environmental response and consumer behavior

In recent times, efforts are being made toward environmental protection and green growth. Purchasing environmentally sustainable products and recycling have gained well-deserved attention and are some of the various eco-friendly consumers' buying behavior. A wide variety of industries has quickly adapted and is focused on green advertising by consumers, regulators, and business stakeholders (Davis, 1994). Whenever there is talk of the green revolution, the consumer is one of the most important factors to consider. The

challenge all companies face is the integration/incorporation of environmental awareness in their business activities and strategies which includes green advertising. There is skepticism and some consumers in different countries question the credibility of green advertising because of 'Greenwashing'. Although some consumers are reluctant in accepting content credibility, Green Advertising has had positive results for organizations and businesses when presented efficiently and effectively (Niazi, Siddiqui, Alishah, & Hunjra, 2012). This is one of the reasons why Green Advertising can be used to make consumers aware of already existing environmentally friendly products which can shape consumers' orientation towards viable consumption. Studies have shown that when the influence of information, entertainment, and inconvenience is higher so is the casual relationship among advertising attitudes (Davis, 1994).

In some studies, on consumer behavior toward advertisements on commercial websites, research confirmed that the following positively affected the appeal of the advertisement; Information & Entertainment, Reliability & Convenience. The reliability of green advertising has a major effect on the consumer's intention to buy eco-friendly products; this is the green advertising's effect on purchase goals among buyers. Credibility can be defined as a characteristic in promotions, meaning the buyers or the consumers can trust the promotion (Shojaee, Totonkavan, & Sanjani, 2014). It is an important antecedent variable among many others that should be examined in research on advertising. Additionally, the credibility of the advertisement /promotion can greatly impact and influence the consumer's behavior toward the advertisement and the advertised brand. Informatively, on the other hand, means that buyers have the access to relevant information when he/she is buying the service or the product. The information should be relevant so that the consumer can make an informed decision. For example, detailed product descriptions and features on the product (Niazi et al., 2012).

Advertising is an important tool and when looking at it from a consumer's point of view, we can maximize consumer satisfaction when buying products by providing the right information and this is where the power of advertising lies (Davis, 1994). Emotional appeal is another key factor that can positively or negatively influence a consumer's attitude towards a product/service, environmental behaviors, and its response to economically friendly advertisements. After these findings, we can safely say that emotional attributes are one of the key attributes of green advertisements among other Cognitive attributes (Niazi et al., 2012). According to another study Environmentally Responsible Consumer Behavior and Green Advertising, if we are looking to promote consumer action then factors of message effectiveness, delivery, and design attractiveness along with originality should be improved. Advertising attributes consisted of the following: Entertainment, Informational Aspect, Compensatory Aspects, personalization, Utility, Security, and Inconvenience. All of these attributes with the exception of security can positively or negatively affect a consumer's intention of purchasing the product or service (Shojaee et al., 2014). The purchase intention of the consumers is significantly affected by green advertising according to the study. When a consumer is quick to adapt and accept an environmentally sound product, lifestyle, or consumption pattern when compared to others then this is known as Eco-Friendly Consumer Innovativeness. Studies have suggested that Eco-Friendly Consumer Innovativeness should be the key factor when you are distinguishing innovative consumers. Furthermore, Consumer Innovates can affect environmentally friendly products' acceptance (Niazi et al., 2012).

Relationship between brand awareness and consumer behavior

Brand awareness is the earliest level of knowledge of a brand, including at least recognition of the brand name or a shape that has been created on information that is in detail. Brand awareness results to make the decision of customers about a product. If a customer going to purchase something he definitely thinks about a brand (Tsuji, Bennett, & Leigh, 2009). Brand awareness is the primitive and the leading restriction in any brand-associated search and it is the potential of a customer to acknowledge and remember a brand in a different circumstance. If the customer has knowledge regarding his brand, he will have more chances for purchasing and he will always make decisions economic wise (Domazet, Đokić, & Milovanov, 2017). Every Company has its major goal to make its brand strong among many brands. And it's not only impact on the short-term profit but also it will be fruitful in a long time. Therefore, the main objective of any good organization team is to combine a brand in order to work out at least for many years and can add up new services/Products (Tsuji et al., 2009).

The brand name is the main thing that fascinates a customer about a brand. If the firm has an interesting brand name so definitely customers will inspire to purchase that product (Clark, Doraszelski, & Draganska, 2009). A productive advertisement/commercial definitely helps the company to build awareness regarding a brand. The impact of advertisement/commercial is consistently on a large scale. An interesting advertisement/commercial always brings more consumers and if any one consumer will be happy after watching an interesting advertisement, then he/she will advertise the brand by Word of Mouth (Domazet et al., 2017). The Famous person who is endorsing the brand is also playing a major role in advertising the product. firms hire celebrities as their brand ambassadors to attract people to the brand. The discount and advertising also raise awareness about the brand. Firms do many things to promote their brand. for instance, they give a free gift, free samples for testing, providing their product as a gift with an additional product, that product which is popular in the market of their own brand or in association with any other Firm (Percy & Rossiter, 1992).

The customer plays an important role in the financial set-up as he pays to purchase the goods or facilities produced. If customers need a product is not their maker will stop having the inspiration to produce and that thing will impact the financial system. Buying purpose means to plan to purchase a good quality or attain a facility. It is about the aspiration of a Consumer to purchase a specific product of a particular brand (Domazet et al., 2017). Customers sometimes purchase on their gut feelings and the selection is done at the store. This kind of selection may classify as an unexpected purchasing decision. A Customer's buying purpose is based on the stage of satisfaction, he looks forward and collects. If the brand makes happy the customer, will become a regular consumer of that specific brand and do something for your brand may be some kind of promotion but if not, the customer might participate in the negative marketing of the brand which would be unfortunate for any brand (Clark et al., 2009). The standard of quality expected and brand faithfulness are extremely connected to each other and certainly affect the intention of a buyer. One more way it plays a very important role that impacts the buy intention is the awareness of buying a product which makes the decision easier (Domazet et al., 2017).

There are many types of customers which make them different from others like price-sensitive customers are always fascinated more the economical/low price products. But there is also a customer who goes for quality over the price they are likely to prefer to purchase the low-price product regardless of its quality. These types of customers believe that only high-cost products are high quality (Clark et al., 2009). An interesting packaging is also playing a major role to attract the customer to the product a well-packed and well-advertised brand makes the product always a preferable option over a poorly packed product. Customer behavior is not only impacting the requirement and purpose to build it also encourages the maker to innovate the production. Ahead of launching any product a maker must have a sound detail regarding his customer and their purchasing behavior (Domazet et al., 2017). A Customer passes through a lot of steps while purchasing any product. The understanding of Customer behavior helps out the marketers to the response of what, where, when, how, and why of the utilization of the product (Percy et al., 1992).

Relationship between sensory stimulated advertising and consumer behavior

The significance of sensory experience in customer attitude has been identified in recent times by the sensory field advertising (Krishna, 2011). Although, there have been useful perceptions of multi-sensory impacts on calculations as in memory and perception of the customer (Hartnett, Romaniuk & Kennedy, 2016). It is crucial for advertisers to attract attention from customers for the purpose of achieving their aims, by linking the name of the brand with particular consumption situations. Advertisers have three key sensory cues to recognize the brand in video advertising (Elder & Krishna, 2010). Visual sensory cues connect the eyes of the customer through visually showing the name, packaging, logo of the brand, or the unique connected distinctive objects of the brand as well (Hartnett et al., 2016). Auditory sensory cues connect the ear of the customer by showing the brand through the audio track advertisement e.g., visual brand name or slogan, special music, or jingle (Elder et al., 2010). Yet, in video advertisements, audio-only sensory cues are very uncommon (Hartnett et al., 2016). And rather than using audio only, advertisers use audio plus visual sensory cues (Elder et al., 2010).

Both audio and visual sensory cues for the identification of a brand give experiences for both the ears and the eyes by showing the associated sound of the brand and the brand itself at the same time (Krishna, 2011). In recent research, scholars thought that visual sensory cues are considered the default in video advertising like they are very common (Hartnett et al., 2016). It should be noticed that automatic awareness is considered as adjusted for the purpose of repeating exposure to the stimulus. Therefore, the initial sensory cue discovering the particular brand will be utilized so that the customers have had left with no options to habituate this sensory cue (Elder et al., 2010). The customer Psychology section is running to acknowledge the importance of bodily experiences as an information source for customers, and the significance of embodied awareness for sensory advertising (Hartnett et al., 2016). Customer behavior can be attracted by sensory advertising for the purpose of generating experience at every level of the purchasing process: awareness about the product and services, activation of desire, product and service assessment related to various other choices, buying, post buying evaluation of consumption or use (Elder et al., 2010).

Studies have shown that the involvement of various senses can have a variety of effects on perceptions when the question senses try to communicate synergistic texts (Krishna, 2011). Particularly, every sensory stimulus strengthens the messages delivered through all the others, providing rise to stronger, more holistic, and more consistent. This integrated growth of sensory effects improves the customer's perception, entering it deeper into the customer's memory (Elder et al., 2010). Therefore, Multi-sensory perceptions facilitate speeder product identification as well as attribution in return to stimulate, and greater processing fasts and a better consequently assessment of the message (Hartnett et al., 2016). The key strategic aim of sensory advertising is to communicate the image of the brand, or sensory branding (Elder et al., 2010).

The aim of sensory advertising is to use the five senses to reinforce the attributes, emotional benefits, functions of the value of the product and send its relevance to the customers and help them to communicate the identity of the brand, though at the same point, communicating the differential value of the product for a particular segment of consumers in a growing competitive market (Hartnett et al., 2016). Sensory advertising is created by a sensory strategy, which shows which particular sense will be or should be used in the image communication and interlinks each sense with the customer, which also explains the experiences as well as messages to be created by each sense (Elder et al., 2010). The main part of sensory advertising is the production of a brand's sensory signature. The important perception is connected with a product or service (Hartnett et al., 2016). The sensory signature is considered as the identification and differentiation of a product. It conveys the important message that the advertisers wish to communicate to the audience (Krishna, 2011).

Relationship between emotional response and consumer behavior

Emotional appeal is very responsible for making the needs and desires of the consumer effectively influencing their buying behavior. Over the past 10-15 years studies have discovered that emotional advertising can impact the customers spending way and can definitely help the customers to recall (Shimp, 1981). To create such emotions, advertisers use expressive advertising. Emotions are considered a core for inducing sentimental behavior and the most important point of effectiveness of advertising (Shahid & Bilal, 2016). In modern times, the use of emotions in an advertisement plays a significant part in the complete success of campaign advertisements. Some studies show that people don't buy the product for logical reasons; they buy the brand for emotional reasons (Moore & Harris, 1996). Emotional advertisement is considered an important promotional object that influences consumer attention and trigger consumer emotions, perception, and attitude regarding a specific product or service (Shimp, 1981). Emotional advertisement is also considered as it is very simple to understand and engage the attention of potential memories regarding a particular brand. The memories are present in the consumer's back of the mind, and when the customer undergoes a purchasing decision these memories motivate a person to make a final purchase decision (Moore et al., 1996).

Advertisers are now utilizing emotional aspects extensively in advertising to make more sales (Shimp, 1981). Emotional advertising helps the consumer to connect their feelings and emotions with a particular brand. It has the strength to make customers happy as well as sad (Shahid et al., 2016). Every advertisement makes affectionate feedback as naturally all the things we live in our daily lives create an impulsive emotional

response (Shimp, 1981). Advertisers should require acknowledging the indispensable significance of utilizing emotion in advertising. Consumer emotional responses are interlinked to their previous experiences. These familiarities will affect consumer response consequently towards buying decisions (Duncan & Nelson, 1985). The main aim of the advertisement is to show live events and connect and engage people with consumers in a better mood as well as stay longer in the memories the people. When people watch advertisements with emotional aspects, people try to connect them with familiarity in their life (Moore et al., 1996).

That advertisement in which promotional, as well as emotional content, are presently aimed to convince people of psychological social, and physiological needs. Emotional aspects in an advertisement may nurture various emotions ranging from excitement, happiness, love, and humor to fear (Duncan et al., 1985). Emotional advertisement helps to make a strong relationship with the consumer and enhance the loyalty of a brand. Advertisers who want the consumer to experience feel connected as well as an emotional bond with the particular brand (Shimp, 1981). The aim of Emotional advertisement is to trigger the right brain hemisphere which is directly responsible to handle the left side as well as related to the creativity and memory of the mind of a person (Moore et al., 1996). Visual as well as advertisement backgrounds are significant under emotional responses, making a synergy between all these aspects can improve the persuasiveness of communication (Shahid et al., 2016). Applying more than one emotional aspect in the advertisement influence the person's five senses as well as creates a happy consumer. Brands apply various emotions in an advertisement for the purpose of enhancing their persuasiveness (Duncan et al., 1985).

A person's nature strongly experiences various kinds of emotions, ranging between excitement, love, humor, happiness, sadness, anger, and fear. It is the major part of happiness, humor, love, and excitement appeal in emotional factor in advertisement (Moore et al., 1996). Emotional appeal contributes exclusively to making a behavior towards the advertisement, which influences the attribute-oriented of the brand beliefs as well as shaping the behavior towards the brand in itself generally (Shahid et al., 2016). There is an important relationship between people purchasing decisions and emotional advertisements. Due to growing exposure, consumers are now becoming very responsive to emotional advertisement and less responsive to rational appeal (Duncan et al., 1985). Emotional advertisement helps to recall a brand as well as leads to direct buying and repurchase. According to the emotional element under advertisement pick consumers, arouse, attention, and interest, make desire as well as encourage them to make a final buying decision (Moore et al., 1996).

Relationship between product placement and consumer behavior

The salespeople and mercantile organizations highlighted a backup endorsement technique in which real merchandising products are displayed in a fantasy play, movie, or television series as an advertisement technique or product placement pre-owned by advertisers and promoters (Hudson & Hudson, 2006). The usual regular type of product placement can be found in a TV commercial. A useful product placement depends on consideration of customer feedback on the commodities and relies on perception and fondness (Reijmersdal, Neijens, & Smit, 2009). The effect of amusing embedded marketing in the earlier research gives few productive intuitions into this research. Product placement is a type of electronic media scheme fellowship as product placement can be merged with important advertisements to disclose a company's amusement connection (Hudson et al., 2006). The foundational aim of product placement is to invent the latest products and illustrate the usage of products. Therefore, organizations do their best to have experience for their commodities in product placement due to their capacity to distribute optimistic feedback in an unsalable situation (Jung & Childs, 2020).

Product placement optimistically affected customer behaviors, remembrance, and acknowledgment regarding company names displayed in the advertisement. The effect of product placement on customer's memory in the form of several types of product placement, like 'video/only' and 'auditory/ only' demonstrations (Hudson et al., 2006). The outcome shows commodities displayed that is product placement, and highlighted climbed down to more consumer recognition when collating to television advertisements and extra-fine commodities in their look (Williams, Petrosky, Hernandez & Page Jr, 2011). Moreover, customers could easily recognize the goods specified in voice messages rather than what is displayed and seeable (Hudson et al., 2006). Customer's

acknowledgment of product placement relies on the kind of advertising and its manifestation time; important product placement is more productive than several types of nurturing customer's remembrance (Reijmersdal et al., 2009). Product placement kinds had a higher effect on customers' remembrance than the product's manifestation time (Jung et al., 2020).

Studies showed that optimistic feedback in contrast to product placement is drawn to three different conditions. (1) When the product was displayed with TV celebs; (2) when product placement was harmonious with a segment displayed; (3) When the product or services were highlighted (Reijmersdal et al., 2009). Despite the fact that movie scenes containing product placement got more optimistic feedback towards the product or services still they decreased customer remembrance and trademark identification (Jung et al., 2020). Further study has discovered that customer behaviors and recognition power is affected by product placement in television advertisements and computerized games (Reijmersdal et al., 2009). The result of product placement on customers' buying thoughts is that customers had a greater amount of limited buying aim for commodities lodged in advertising (Jung et al., 2020). There is a connection between customers' purchase intentions and buying aim, or that customer brands' consumption and buying might influence buying attitudes (Reijmersdal et al., 2009). Putting products and business names into main media has given rise to huge numbers of finances in the advertisement industry (Williams et al., 2011).

The customer socialization concept, a familiar conceptual work that can be worn to investigate the effect of socialization elements on behaviors on the way to product placement and the following attitude, is beneficial to growing the information of product placement in advertising and familiar customer attitudes (Reijmersdal et al., 2009). Nevertheless, there are several communal elements that have a part in linking with customers' product placement behaviors and buying aims (Williams et al., 2011). The better distinctly the product or brand is used by the celebrity, the better that product will be visible as successful, convincing the audience to buy (Reijmersdal et al., 2009). If the advertisers put more pressure on using product placement, then marketers or advertisers should busily and purposely be in charge of product depiction in advertisements to have surety that customers have agreeable behaviors to the product that might be the expected result to maximize buying aims for the brand or product (Jung et al., 2020).

Conclusion

The above report concluded that advertisement has an important impact on consumer buying behavior. The weak and strong researches of advertisement were explained in the above report in order to analyze the way advertising works. Moreover, some major factors of advertising as brand awareness, product placement, emotional responses, stimulating advertising, and environmental responses were discussed in the above report also their relationship and impact on the consumer buying decision. Generally, how the advertisements influence customers buying intentions was also discussed. Also, advertisements in whatever pattern can have a negative as well as a positive impact on consumer buying intentions. This report above also showed that Brand Awareness plays an important role in consumer buying behavior. Brand awareness has a special effect on buying behavior. Branding a product is more important than how cool your product looks or how attractive your logo is. A Customer's buying purpose is based on the level of satisfaction and as we study brand awareness it does not only impact the short-term profit but also it will be fruitful in the long term and one-thing which fascinates a customer about a brand is the brand name it will inspire the customer to buy that product.

For that purpose, companies make advertisements to build awareness or acknowledge people about their products through advertisement. Advertising companies hire celebrities in their ads according to their product to attract people towards the brand because only famous people make influence people regarding the product. That's why companies go with advertisements to promote their product because it is the best way to reach your targeted audience through advertisement. Also, product placement has been very beneficial and how it is portrayed with the creativity of advertisement. It also includes how it is helping towards sponsoring products. Other than this, marketing activities and doing promotion of the products and how it is connected with the social media mediums so that accurately products are advertised. Moreover, it includes how the audience can connect when the advertisement is advertised during a movie or television and gives the audience awareness of

the product. Furthermore, how product placement is helpful for the audience they want to target without the help of artificial settings.

Most importantly, when the actors in the advertisement use the product, it gives the brand recognition so that audience can easily remember it. We discussed the correlation between Environmental Response and Consumer Behavior. Buying Eco-friendly products is a priority for most consumers and that's why the industry as a whole has quickly evolved and adapted Green Advertising. There is skepticism by some but that is expected when change is being discussed or adopted. Research has shown that Green Advertising does indeed have an effect on a consumer's buying decision and behavior. The intensity of the effect Green Advertising has on a consumer depends on the consumer's mindset towards the planet's well-being. It is concluded that globally, advertisement influences the attitude and behavior of the customer. The customers of durable goods and products have their sources which are advertisements.

References

- Aaker, D. A. (1996). Measuring brand equity across products and markets. *California management review*, 38(3).
- Adelaar, T., Chang, S., Lancendorfer, K. M., Lee, B., & Morimoto, M. (2003). Effects of media formats on emotions and impulse buying intent. *Journal of Information Technology*, 18(4), 247-266.
- Arnould, E. J., & Thompson, C. J. (2005). Consumer culture theory (CCT): Twenty years of research. *Journal of consumer research*, 31(4), 868-882.
- Ayanwale, A. B., Alimi, T., & Ayanbimipe, M. A. (2005). The influence of advertising on consumer brand preference. *Journal of social sciences*, 10(1), 9-16.
- Barroso, A. (2008). Advertising and consumer awareness of a new product. *Centre for Economic Policy Research Paper*, 3, 1-30
- Barroso, A., & Llobet, G. (2012). Advertising and consumer awareness of new, differentiated products. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 49(6), 773-792.
- Chukwu, B. A., Kanu, E. C., & Ezeabogu, A. N. (2019). The impact of advertising on consumers' buying behavior. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 8(1), 1-15.
- Clark, C. R., Doraszelski, U., & Draganska, M. (2009). The effect of advertising on brand awareness and perceived quality: An empirical investigation using panel data. *Qme*, 7(2), 207-236.
- Danaher, P. J., Danaher, T. S., Smith, M. S., & Loaiza-Maya, R. (2020). Advertising effectiveness for multiple retailer brands in multimedia and multichannel environment. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 57(3), 445-467.
- Davis, J. J. (1994). Consumer response to corporate environmental advertising. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*.
- Domazet, I. S., Đokić, I., & Milovanov, O. (2017). The Influence of advertising media on brand awareness. *Management: Journal of Sustainable Business and Management Solutions in Emerging Economies*, 23(1), 13-22.
- Duncan, C. P., & Nelson, J. E. (1985). Effects of humor in a radio advertising experiment. *Journal of Advertising*, 14(2), 33-64.
- Dunn, S. W., & Barban, A. (1987). Advertising, its role in modern marketing advertising.
- Elder, R. S., & Krishna, A. (2010). The effects of advertising copy on sensory thoughts and perceived taste. *Journal of consumer research*, 36(5), 748-756.
- Ginosar, A., & Levi-Faur, D. (2010). Regulating product placement in the European Union and Canada: Explaining regime change and diversity. *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis*, 12(5), 467-490.
- Hartnett, N., Romaniuk, J., & Kennedy, R. (2016). Comparing direct and indirect branding in advertising. *Australasian Marketing Journal (AMJ)*, 24(1), 20-28.
- Hudson, S., & Hudson, D. (2006). Branded entertainment: a new advertising technique or product placement in disguise?. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 22(5-6), 489-504.

- Hussain, S. K., Riaz, K., Kazi, A. K., & Herani, G. M. (2008). Advertising styles' impact on attention in Pakistan.
- Jung, E., & Childs, M. (2020). Destination as product placement: An advertising strategy to impact beliefs and behavioral intentions. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 32(3), 178-193.
- Keller, K. L. (1993). Conceptualizing, measuring, and managing customer-based brand equity. *Journal of Marketing*, 57(1), 1-22.
- Kotler, P., Keller, K. L., Koshy, A., & Jha, M. (2009). Creation of customer value satisfaction and loyalty. *Marketing management*, 13, 120-125.
- Krishna, A. (Ed.). (2011). *Sensory marketing: Research on the sensuality of products*. Routledge.
- Krishna, A., Cian, L., & Sokolova, T. (2016). The power of sensory marketing in advertising. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 10, 142-147.
- Lafferty, B. A., Goldsmith, R. E., & Newell, S. J. (2002). The dual credibility model: The influence of corporate and endorser credibility on attitudes and purchase intentions. *Journal of marketing theory and practice*, 10(3), 1-11.
- Latif, A., & Abideen, Z. U. (2011). Effects of television advertising on children: A Pakistani perspective. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 30(4), 38.
- Lee, C. K. C., Fernandez, N., & Martin, B. A. (2002). Using self-referencing to explain the effectiveness of ethnic minority models in advertising. *International Journal of Advertising*, 21(3), 367-379.
- Moore, D. J., & Harris, W. D. (1996). Affect intensity and the consumer's attitude toward high impact emotional advertising appeals. *Journal of advertising*, 25(2), 37-50.
- Moore, E. S. (2004). Children and the changing world of advertising. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 52(2), 161-167.
- Niazi, G. S. K., Siddiqui, J., Alishah, B., & Hunjra, A. I. (2012). Effective advertising and its influence on consumer buying behavior. *Information management and business review*, 4(3), 114-119.
- Odunsi, R. (2020). The effect of advertising on consumer behavior in Finland.
- Percy, L., & Rossiter, J. R. (1992). A model of brand awareness and brand attitude advertising strategies. *Psychology & Marketing*, 9(4), 263-274.
- Pickett-Baker, J., & Ozaki, R. (2008). Pro-environmental products: marketing influence on consumer purchase decision. *Journal of consumer marketing*.
- Rahmi, A., Tayeb, B., & Amerkhail, S. (2020). The Impact of Advertising on Consumer Buying Behavior.
- Rai, N. (2013). Impact of advertising on consumer behaviour and attitude with reference to consumer durables. *International Journal of Management Research and Business Strategy*, 2(2), 74-79.
- Romaniuk, J., & Sharp, B. (2003). Measuring brand perceptions: Testing quantity and quality. *Journal of targeting, measurement and analysis for marketing*, 11(3), 218-229.
- Segercrantz, M. (2013). Advertising to children in Finland. *Young Consumers*.
- Shahid, M., Bilal, A., & Majid, F. (2016). Get your advertisement noticed; impact of emotional advertisement on consumer buying intention in the presence of consumer emotion management. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*
- Shimp, T. A. (1981). Attitude toward the ad as a mediator of consumer brand choice. *Journal of advertising*, 10(2), 9-48.
- Shojaee, M. R., Totonkavan, S., & Sanjani, N. M. (2014). Investigating the types of e-advertising strategy and its influence on consumer buying behaviour. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(7), 262-266.
- Stephen, A. T., & Coote, L. V. (2005). Brands in action: the role of brand placements in building consumer-brand identification. In *American Marketing Association Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 16, No. 1, p. 28).
- Tsuji, Y., Bennett, G., & Leigh, J. H. (2009). Investigating factors affecting brand awareness of virtual advertising. *Journal of Sport Management*, 23(4), 511-544.

- Van Reijmersdal, E., Neijens, P., & Smit, E. G. (2009). A new branch of advertising: Reviewing factors that influence reactions to product placement. *Journal of advertising research*, 49(4), 429-449.
- Wei, M., Liu, M., Xu, J., Li, S., & Cao, J. (2022). Understanding the influence of sensory advertising of tourism destinations on visit intention with a modified AIDA model. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 27(3), 259-273.
- Williams, K., Petrosky, A., Hernandez, E., & Page Jr, R. (2011). Product placement effectiveness: revisited and renewed. *Journal of Management and Marketing research*, 7, 1.
- Wright, S. A. (2016). Reinvestigating the endorser by product matchup hypothesis in advertising. *Journal of Advertising*, 45(1), 26-32.